

LEXICOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL TERMS (BASED ON ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)

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Annotation: The article provides a general understanding of phraseological terms and analyzes of various scientists in this field. An attempt was made to prove the theories through examples of phraseological terms in English and Uzbek languages.

Key words: phraseological units, phraseological terms, idiom, vocabulary, proverbs, wise words.

Not all phraseological terms can be directly translated. According to Collins (the author of the book "Books of English Idioms"), the phraseological units in the English language that are used today in written and spoken speech it is an important part of the language that enriches and decorates the language. At the same time, it is an important and based element that is carefully used in a particular language. Careful use is an important caveat, as a speech that is too full of phrases loses its appeal. Despite the fact that they are brought into the speech ready, too much repetition of them makes the speech lose its luster and become stale. Also, the general meaning cannot be understood through the meaning of these word units themselves.

There are important features of phraseological terms, which are:

1. Lack of motivation, that is, meaning
2. Stability of lexical components

What is meant by motivation in phraseological terms? Motivation is a meaning, and if the words in the phrase have a common meaning, it is called "motivated". Here are some examples:

"A dark horse" means "a dark horse" in direct translation, but its idiomatic meaning is "a person about whom no one knows anything."

The literal translation of "A white elephant" is "white elephant", and the idiomatic meaning is "spending money on unnecessary things".

In the Uzbek language, the word idiom is mainly used for phraseology. In particular, in Shavkat Rahmatullayev's explanatory phraseological dictionary of the Uzbek language, it is said to be a phrase and mainly verb combinations are given. For example;

"Like pulling hair from dough" means easy

The "seed of the ango" is a hard-to-find fruit, and the ango is a fruit mentioned only in legends.

As it can be seen from the given examples, in my opinion, idioms in the Uzbek language can be considered semi-motivated. Because its meaning can be understood based on the meaning of the words themselves, the meaning has not been completely transferred to something else. It is also difficult to find an exact equivalent when translating phrases from English. In general, the origin and use of each phraseological term depends on the culture of that language nation. Accordingly, various discussions have arisen regarding the naming of phraseological terms, and the terms are also found in different ways. For example: -set expressions

- phrases

- set phrases
- fixed word groups
- collocations.

The stability of phraseological units means the degree of invariance of the variety of phraseological units.

Minimum stability indicators at the phraseological level:

-sustainability of use, ie. that phraseological units are not separate expressions used only by this or that author, but language units that are the common property of a certain community;

- structural-semantic stability, which is based on the stability of the lexical composition of phraseological units, their lack of structural-semantic modeling. It is formed both structurally and semantically according to the models characteristic of a certain stage of language development.

- the stability of the lexical composition of fully or partially revised meaning and phraseological units.

- syntactic stability manifested in stable word order of phraseological units.

It should be noted that the completely or partially revised direct meaning of the components, stability of use, structural and semantic modeling is combined with the following phenomena depending on the type of phraseological units:

invariance of the lexical composition of phraseological units;

- the presence of the same invariant meaning in phraseological variants;

- the presence of semantic invariance, that is, common meaning with possible differences in structural synonyms;

-variant phraseological units have a lexical invariant, that is, an important word that cannot be replaced;

Most Russian scientists use the term Phraseologic units introduced by Academician Vinogradov. Western scientists use the term idioms, but according to the explanations given in Russian linguistics, it is only a part of phraseological units. Russian scientist V. Vinogradov semantically classifies phraseological units based on their meaning and divides them into 3 types:

1. Phraseological fusions - these are units, the general meaning of which cannot be deduced from the meaning of the word composition. . The meaning of phraseological fusions is considered unmotivated at the current stage of language development: red tape (bureaucrats), a mare's nest (distraction).

2. Phrasal units - these are expressions, meaning can be deduced from the composition of words. The general meaning is based on the figurative meaning. to show one's teeth, to stand to one's guns. They are motivational expressions.

3. Phraseological collocations - these are phraseological combinations, not only motivated, but one of the words is used in the correct sense, while the other has a figurative meaning. to meet requirement to attain success

In this group of phraseological units, some parts may not lose their figurative meaning. For example: to meet the needs, to meet the demand, to meet the necessity; to have success, to lose success (demand, offer, be forced). These combinations are not synonymous and the general meaning changes, but the meaning of the main word does not change.

Professor A.I. Smirnitsky structurally classifies phraseological units and characterizes them semantically and grammatically as highly idiomatic word descriptors that function as word equivalents. It offers 3 types of available phrases:

1. Traditional phrases (nice distinction, rough sketch);
2. Phraseological combinations - phraseological structures (to fall in love, to get up);
3. Idioms (to wash one's dirty linen in public);

Divides the second group into two more subgroups:

1. one-top phraseological units, that is, they consist of one main word;

a) verb: to give up, to bring up, to try out, to look up, to drop in, etc;

b) to be helpful: to be surprised, to be up to, etc;

c) prepositional phrases: by heart.

2. two-top phraseological units, i.e. composed of compound words. These units can be equivalent to a noun, a verb or an adverb:

brain trust, white elephant, blind alley;

to know the ropes, to take place;

ups and downs, rough and ready, flat as a pancake.

Phraseological units completely or partially change their meaning, and phraseological units are used in their literary sense. Both of them are characterized by their phraseological stability, which differs from free phrases and compound words. Prof. A.V. Kunin developed the theory of stagnation according to the following aspects:

1. Stability of usage- a phraseological unit that is not created in the speech and is processed in the speech;

2. Lexical stability- partially or completely in phraseological variation is a composition of unrepeatable phraseological units.

According to the following classification, the phrases change and the meaning does not change:

Lexical: a skeleton in the cupboard / closet (family secret), a blind pig / tiger (illegal sale of alcohol);

Grammatical: to be in deep water / waters (to be in a difficult situation), a stony heart – a heart of stone (cruel nature);

Positional: a square peg in a round hole – a round peg in a square hole

the t's – to cross one's t's and dot one's i's (to ensure the correctness of all arguments);

Quantitative: Tom, Dick and Harry – every Tom, Dick and Harry (someone and everyone);

Mixed variants: raise/stir up the nest of hornets' nest about one's ears – to arouse/stir up the nest of hornets.

3. Semantic stability is based on lexical stability of phraseological units. Despite some changes, the meaning of the phrase is preserved. It can be strong, weak, definite or vague.

4. Syntactic stability. In this case, the characteristics of phraseological units can be as follows:

1. Prepared copy;

2. Structural division;

3. Morphological instability;

4. Immutability of lexical content;

5. Semantic unity;
6. Syntactic flexibility.

or a stable group of words whose meaning has partially changed"

Phraseological units are divided into four subclasses according to their function in communication determined by their structural-semantic characteristics:

1. Referential phraseological units take the place of certain concepts: a bull in a china shop (rude man);

2. Indicative phraseological units that take the place of specific concepts and can be used in the passive structure: to cross the Rubicon – the Rubicon is crossed!

3. Exclamatory phraseological units, exclamation replaces concepts: a pretty (nice) kettle of fish! For crying out loud!

4. It is used instead of communicative phraseological units, sentences (proverbs or sayings). For example;

Still waters run deep.

The world is a nice place.

Communicative phraseological units represent a situation: A proverb is a set of words, sentences or phrases that give advice or express general truths:

Idleness is the root of all evil - God is tired of Bekochi;

A penny saved is a penny gained - Little by little there will be a river;

The pen is mightier than the sword - The word is stronger than the sword;

Ask no questions, hear no lies - Too much talk is a disaster;

Silence is something an answer

As can be seen from the above classifications, all the sentences and combinations that are used in a figurative sense and are ready for speech are phraseological units and include all stable units, proverbs and wise words, phrases and idioms. The phraseological layer of each language is formed based on the culture, customs and way of life of that language nation and enriches its own language. Phraseology is an extremely complex phenomenon, and its study requires a unique research method, as well as the use of information from other disciplines - lexicology, grammar, stylistics, phonetics, language history, history, philosophy, logic, and regional studies. Linguists have different opinions on a number of phraseology problems, and this is natural. Nevertheless, the important task of linguists working in the field of phraseology is to unite efforts and find a common language in the interests of both the theory of phraseology and the practice of teaching foreign languages. The phraseological fund of the English language is so large that its complete study does not correspond to the scope of this work. Nevertheless, using the example of the considered phraseological units, it is possible to clearly imagine how diverse the semantics and expressiveness of phraseological units in modern English are. Thanks to the literary works of writers and poets both in Great Britain and around the world, the English language now has a large number of phraseological units. But it should not be forgotten that a lot of phraseological units from the history and culture of different countries of the world entered the English language.

References:

1. Kunin A.V. English phraseology. Theoretical course. - M., 1981.2. Kunin A.V. Modern English Phraseology. - M.: International relations, 1996.

2. Kunin A.V. English-Russian phraseological dictionary. 3rd ed., Stereotype.
3. Smirnitsky A.I. Lexicology of the English language. - M., 1996.
4. Vinogradov V.S. Introduction to Translation Studies. 2001.
5. Kunin A.V. Course of phraseology of contemporary English language.-M. 1986.
6. Narimonova Z. About the translation of phraseological expressions.-T.:OzMU collection. 2007.
7. Oxford dictionary of idioms Published in the United States by Oxford University Press Inc., New York © Oxford University Press 1999, 2004
8. Isaeva, M. A., & Eshonkhojaeva, V. J. (2021). ANALYSIS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL METHODS OF STUDYING FAMILY RELATIONS. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 1(Special Issue 2), 109-115.
9. Isayeva, M. A. (2014). Religious And Psychological Aspects Of Family Functions. The Way of Science, 90.
10. Rakhmatullayev Sh. Phraseological dictionary of the Uzbek language. - T.: Editor-in-Chief of Komuslar. 1982.
11. Alisherovna, M. K. (2021). Car transport an approach to the research of the essence of investment activities of enterprises. Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research, 10(5), 415-418.
12. Mukhitdinova, K. A. (2020). The Importance of Sources of Financing of Transportation System. In НАУКА 2020. Теория И Практика (pp. 23-25).
13. Alisherovna, M. K. (2020). Analysis and evaluation of sources of investment in automotive transport enterprises. South Asian Journal Of Marketing & Management Research, 10(4), 74-78.
14. Mukhitdinova, K. (2022). Increasing the Efficiency of Investment Activities of Automotive Enterprises. International Finance and Accounting, 2022(1), 20.